

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

INDIVIDUAL AND COMBINATIVE EFFECTS OF SHORT-TERM INCUBATION OF BARLEY SEEDLINGS IN NA-ISOCATIONIC SALT SOLUTIONS ON Q6PDH ENZYME ACTIVITY

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Abstract

The division and growth of cells in the leaves, roots and stems of plants planted in saline soils slows down, therefore the development of plants is weakened, the growth rate of the leaf surface decreases and, as a result, the intensity of photosynthesis decreases. Continued stress can completely stop the development and growth of plants. In addition to reducing plant growth, salt stress causes chlorosis, necrotic spots, yield and quality reduction.

Keywords: Stress, Saline soils, incubation, activity level

The influence of different concentrations of NaCl, Na₂SO₄, NaHCO₃ salts on the activity dynamics of the cytoplasmic form of Q6PDH enzyme in the roots of barley sprouts during 24 hours is reflected in table 1 presented below. As can be seen from the results presented in the table, the level of activity of the Q6PDH enzyme in the sprouts of the control variant remained at a fairly high level at all stages of the

incubation period, and a stable increase in its activity, albeit weak, was observed. At the end of the incubation period, this increase was about 7.3% compared to the initial stage. Apparently, such a noticeable feature in the activity dynamics of the enzyme is related to the stable demand for its catalytic activity during this period of barley sprout development.

Table 1

**Short-term growth of barley seedlings in Na-isocationic salt solutions
the effect of incubation on the activity of Q6PDH enzyme**

Variants	Incubation time (hours)				
	3	6	12	18	24
Control	262±4	266±5	271±3	275±4	281±3
NaCl					
50 mM	251±3	283±7	298±4	301±5	304±7
100 mM	237±4	302±5	381±4	426±7	432±6
150 mM	223±5	326±3	385±5	232±5	194±5
200 mM	196±6	341±8	260±6	101±3	56±2
Na₂SO₄					
50 mM	245±3	326±7	395±5	390±8	378±11
100 mM	233±9	313±3	252±7	214±6	211±3
150 mM	199±7	222±5	151±8	112±2	105±5
200 mM	178±7	203±3	113±2	61±3	32±1
NaHCO₃					
50 mM	270±12	311±12	312±7	188±7	144±2
100 mM	275±5	334±9	283±5	153±4	101±3
150 mM	277±7	302±6	231±3	81±2	54±3
200 mM	269±9	296±6	184±4	35±1	33±2

The addition of NaCl salt to the medium led to a significant weakening of the activity of the Q6PDH enzyme in the first periods of incubation. A direct correlation was observed between the concentration of NaCl salt and the degree of inhibition of activity. During the incubation period of 3 hours, the maximum inhibition occurred at 200 mM concentration of NaCl salt, and at this time the activity decreased by 25.2% compared to the control.

Starting from the six-hour incubation period, the effect of NaCl salt on the activity of Q6PDH enzyme

changed dramatically. Due to the continuation of the incubation stage at relatively low concentrations of salt (50-100 mM), the activity of the enzyme gradually increased and reached its maximum at the end of the experiments. The stimulating effect of NaCl at a concentration of 150 mM on the activity of the enzyme was limited to the 6-12 hour stage, and in the later stages it was replaced by the inhibiting effect. At a concentration of 200 mM of NaCl, its stimulating effect on the enzyme activity was shorter-term, after 6 hours of incubation, the enzyme activity was sharply lost, and

at the end of the experiment, only 20% of the activity in the control remained.

The inhibitory effect of NaCl salt on the activity of the Q6PDH enzyme in the first stages of the incubation process is probably due to the direct effect of the salt on the enzyme protein. The activation of the enzyme by NaCl at later stages seems to be due to triggering the induction of its biosynthesis. Perhaps this phenomenon is due to the neutralization of the negative effect of salt on the cell. The sharp negative effect of the high concentration of NaCl on the activity of the enzyme can be explained by the excessive degree of damage and the restriction of the cell's defense system, including the participation of the Q6PDH enzyme in this process.

The effect of Na₂SO₄ salt on the activity dynamics of the Q6PDH enzyme is similar to the effect of NaCl. The main noticeable difference between the effects of both salts on the course of this process is that the activation and ginger effect of Na₂SO₄ is stronger than that of NaCl salt, and these effects are obtained at relatively low concentrations of Na₂SO₄ salt.

The effect of NaHCO₃ salt on the activity dynamics of Q6PDH enzyme of barley sprouts was different from that of NaCl and Na₂SO₄. Firstly, in the first stage of incubation, the effect of inhibition characteristic of NaCl and Na₂SO₄ variants is not observed in this case, on the contrary, NaHCO₃ increases the activity of the enzyme, even if it is slight. Secondly, even at relatively small concentrations of NaHCO₃, the stimulating effect of salt on the activity of the enzyme disappears, and in the later stages, the activity of the enzyme decreases sharply compared to the control in direct proportion to the concentration of salt. It seems that the stimulation of Q6PDH enzyme activity by NaHCO₃ in the first periods of incubation is due to the increase of intracellular pH of cells due to the effect of this salt on the one hand, and on the other hand, the optimal pH of the enzyme is relatively higher than the neutral environment (pH-8.1). The sharp negative changes in the activity of the enzyme in the later stages are probably due to the fact that this salt is more toxic to the cells of barley sprouts than NaCl and Na₂SO₄ salts.

Thus, the activity of the cytoplasmic form of the enzyme Q6PDH in the roots of barley sprouts at a certain concentration limit is significantly increased as a result of the stress caused by NaCl Na₂SO₄ and NaHCO₃ salts, and it decreases sharply at high concentrations of salts. Considering that the main product of the catalytic effect of the Q6PDH enzyme on its substrate is NADPH, it can be concluded that the increase in its activity is due to the increase in the demand for NADPH in the elimination of the stress created by salts. The weakness in the activity of the enzyme at high concentrations of salts is apparently related to the difficulty of the activity of the Q6PDH enzyme itself due to the excessive stress factor.

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